

LOW-ENERGY ELECTRON BEAM CURED THERMOSET TAPE PLACEMENT

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1 Introduction

Thermoset composite materials are used to a large extend today and automated thermoset tape placement machines are used to pre-form large-scale structures like wind turbines, ship structures and aerospace components. After pre-forming of the material, the complete mold structure is bagged and placed in an oven or autoclave to cure, depending on the desired performance. The automated placement of the material allows consistent part quality while the traditional autoclave based thermal curing method for thermoset composites faces critical challenges with the increasing of size and thickness of composite parts [1, 2]:

- long curing cycles with high energy consumption.
- non-uniform curing of parts with large residual stresses due to the unavoidable temperature gradients
- large capital investment and operating expense.

Moreover, in many cases, an oven or an autoclave that is big enough for the composite part is not available or has limited availability. One good example is the "world's largest" autoclave (working area: \varnothing 9 m \times 25 m) developed by "ASC Process Systems" company to satisfy the curing demands from the Boeing-787's fuselage and wing skin carbon-fiber/epoxy parts [3]. The size limitation of autoclave is a great challenge to large-size polymer composites, which is limiting increased use of polymer composites in the wind and aerospace industry.

Researchers and industries have long desired to explore and develop low cost out-of-autoclave (OOA) composite fabrication methods and

investigated different curing alternatives, including x-ray, γ -ray [4, 5], ultraviolet [6, 7], microwave [8, 9], electron beam (EB) curing [10-12] and etc. The detailed overview of different curing methods, including the application status and existing challenges for advanced polymer composites will be published soon in another paper from the author [13].

EB curing was explored as a very attractive alternative for out-of-autoclave (OOA) production of high-performance polymer composite materials. Since AEROSPATIALE company of France firstly investigated the EB curing of advanced composites for aerospace applications from the early 1970s and manufactured a missile fuel tank by EB curing [4], the application of EB curing for advanced polymer composites has obtained great development and several airplane parts, including bulkhead and wing skin, were successfully manufactured [10, 14]. However, traditional EB curing of thermoset composites after complete layup needs high-energy electrons (5-15 MeV) to penetrate the whole thickness of the part, so the curing process needs to be finished in a proper shielded irradiation house. The curing process needs large capital costs for the high-energy EB emitters, and the concrete walls and ceiling to shield x-rays which are produced as a by-product of the EB process. Besides, because of the non-uniform dose distribution of the high-energy EB through the material and reaction exotherm generated inside, non-uniform curing, uneven mass shrinkage, and void and bubble formation occurs, which lead to an improper consolidation of the fiber/resin composite media. If the composites are thick and exotherm is high, catastrophic thermal degradation of the matrix material may occur

resulting in potentially hazardous processing conditions and a terminally damaged composite product.

Aiming at the high operating & maintaining costs and poor curing homogeneity existed in the high-energy EB curing method, this paper explored a new low-energy EB cured tape placement process for OOA fabrication of thermoset composites. This process integrates automated tape placement method with a self-shielded low-energy (150 KeV) EB irradiation unit for the on-line curing of the prepregs. The tape placement process provides significant consolidation pressure during the curing which is not available in the standard EB curing of composites, so enough consolidation and adhesion between layers can be achieved simultaneously during the tape layup.

A low-energy EB cured tape placement system was set up and irradiation process was optimized to obtain a homogenous curing of the prepreg. The curing behavior of composites by low-energy EB irradiation was characterized, and the effect of processing parameters, including exposure dose and post-heating, on interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) was investigated experimentally. Finally, composite plates with an ILSS of maximum 63 MPa were obtained.

The layer-wise low-energy EB curing tape placement method in this paper provides a low-cost and efficient way to fabricate thermoset composite laminates without autoclave processing and it has a great industrial application potential for high performance composite areas. Besides, this method allows the fabrication of large structures with low energy consumption, more flexibility and simplicity compared to the large capital and tooling expenditures, poor curing homogeneity and size restrictions inherent in autoclave curing.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

EB curable prepregs were prepared with EB-sensitive epoxy resin EB99-1 (Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials, China) and carbon fiber T700 (TORAY, Japan) in Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials, China. The fabricated

prepreg have a fiber surface density of $130 \pm 5 \text{ g/m}^2$, resin content of $35 \pm 3 \%$ and thickness of 0.125 mm.

2.2 Fabrication process of composites

Composite laminates were fabricated by the setup illustrated in figure 1. After being irradiated to a certain dose with low-energy EB emitters, the irradiated EB curable prepregs were immediately compacted on the mold surface by tape placement machine. The low-energy EB emitters are provided by Advanced Electron Beams, Inc., USA. The emitting energy and beam current parameters of the emitters are adjustable in the range 80-150 KeV and 0-25 mA. The tape placement machine used for the experiment is developed in the State Key Lab for Manufacturing Systems Engineering, Xi'an Jiaotong University, China. The tape placement machine can place multiple prepregs simultaneously, with a maximum placement speed of 30 m/min and compaction force of 1200 N. The placement speed and compaction force used for the experiment is 5 m/min and $1100 \pm 25 \text{ N}$.

Fig. 1. Illustration of low-energy EB cured thermoset tape placement process

Fig. 2. Low-energy EB irradiation unit and tape placement system

2.3 EB exposure dose

The surface exposure dose of composites D (KGy) is calculated according to the equation (1).

$$D = \frac{K \cdot I}{S} \quad (1)$$

Where K (KGy m/min/mA) is the application efficiency coefficient of emitter, which is a combined factor of EB acceleration voltage, irradiation air gap, ambient gas species and emitter efficiency. I (mA) is the beam current, and S (m/min) is the irradiation speed of the prepreg.

Dosimeters (GEX Corporation, USA) were used to measure the actual irradiated dose on the surface of the material and K factor was calculated to characterize the application efficiency for a specified application parameters.

2.4 Dose-depth distribution

Electrons interact much more strongly with matter than photons in electromagnetic radiation. Unlike photon absorption in electromagnetic irradiation, an individual electron is a charged particle which can lose part of its energy while continuing to travel deeper into the irradiated material. There is no single equation that can accurately describe the drop of electron energy, but the maximum depth of penetration (D_m) of an electron into a homogeneous material can be estimated using the empirically-derived Kanaya-Okayama equation [15]:

$$D_m = \frac{k \cdot A \cdot E_0^{1.67}}{Z^{0.89} \cdot \rho} \quad (2)$$

Where: k is a unit-dependent constant; Z and A are the average atomic number and atomic mass of the material; ρ is the average material density; E_0 is the initial electron energy.

As the dosimeter is composed of organic material which can be considered approximately have the same atomic number and atomic mass with prepreg material, the penetration depth of electrons in prepreg (D_p) and in dosimeters (D_d) can be correlated as below:

$$\frac{D_p}{D_d} = \frac{\rho_d}{\rho_p} \quad (3)$$

Where: ρ_p is the average density of prepreg, ρ_d is the average density of dosimeters used in this test.

Therefore, for an irradiation air gap of 13mm between the emitter and composite prepreg in the setup, the dose-depth characteristics of several different incident EB energies were measured by a stack of dosimeters (density: 1 g/cm³, thickness: 17.8 ± 0.2 μm), as illustrated in figure 3. Dose-depth distribution for prepreg (average density 1.6 g/cm³) was calculated according to the equation (2) and (3).

Fig.3. Configuration for measurement of EB dose-depth distribution by stacked dosimeters

2.5 Degree of cure & Tg

As the EB curing of prepreg is an exothermic reaction, so the exothermic heat generated during the curing process can directly represent the percentage of cure. The residual exothermic heat of the prepreg material which is irradiated with different EB dose was measured in a differential scanning calorimeter (Mettler-Toledo, Switzerland), with a scanning rate of 20 K/min in a nitrogen atmosphere. The residual heat was taken to be a direct measure of the material not cured under the EB. The same EB curable formulation was also thermally cured in DSC to measure the total heat of reaction. The degree of cure α as a function of dose was obtained according to the equation (4):

$$\alpha = \left[\frac{H_T - H_R}{H_T} \right] \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Where α (%) is the degree of cure, H_T is the total heat of reaction, and H_R is the residual heat of irradiated samples.

This procedure is based on the assumption that the total heat of reaction for 100% EB cured material is same as that for 100 % thermal curing. Previous studies have shown that similar Tg obtained for both 100 % thermally cured composite and EB cured composite that was subsequently thermally post-cured, and proved that this is a reasonable assumption [16].

The glass transition temperature was measured by multi-frequency temperature modulated DSC (*TOPEM*[®]) from Mettler-Toledo (Switzerland). The scanning rate is 1 K/min.

2.6 Interlaminar shear strength

The mechanical properties of the composites were analyzed in terms of the ILSS. Centre-loaded short beam shear tests were conducted according to ASTM D2344 [17]. Samples were tested on a 3-point bend fixture at 1.0 mm/min in the INSTRON 1195. The interlaminar short beam shear strength (τ_{sbs}), MPa, was calculated using equation (5).

$$\tau_{sbs} = \frac{3P}{4w \cdot t} \quad (5)$$

Where P is the maximum load, w is the specimen width, and t is the thickness of the specimen.

3 Results & Discussion

3.1 Dose-depth distribution

During the high-energy EB irradiation process, the dose-depth distribution within the composite material is similar to a downward-opened parabola curve: the EB dose increases first to maximum then begins to decrease during the penetration in the material [18]. Unlike the high-energy EB, low-energy EB generates remarkable dose gradient across the thickness of materials, and thus the dose steadily decreases across the thickness. Figure 4 shows the original measured EB dose-depth distribution curve in the stacked dosimeters; figure 5 shows the calculated EB penetration curve in the prepeg.

Fig. 4. EB dose-depth distribution in stacked dosimeters

Fig. 5. EB dose-depth distribution in prepeg

As a result of the energy attenuation of an incident EB in the irradiated prepeg materials, the radiation curing behaviors inside the composite materials embody some particular effects of irradiation technology. The characteristics of irradiation process could lead to non-uniformity in the crosslinking structure and have an overall detrimental influence on the properties of the resulting resin and its composites. Therefore, double-sided irradiation was considered more suitable to get a uniform dose distribution across the prepeg thickness.

The measured dose-depth distribution curves for single emitter were fitted by high-order polynomials and synthesized to get double-sided dose-depth curves for different emitting voltages as shown in figure 6.

Fig. 6. EB dose-depth distribution in prepreg for double-sided irradiation

3.2 Effect of EB dose on curing degree and Tg

Like the effect of temperature for a thermal curing material, the EB dose is very critical for the cure and final properties of EB-curable prepreg. Therefore, the effect of EB exposure dose on curing degree and Tg was investigated in the first step.

Fig. 7. Correlation of EB exposure dose vs. curing degree

Fig. 8. Correlation of EB exposure dose vs. Tg

Figure 7 and 8 shows the correlation of EB exposure dose versus curing degree and Tg. According to the curves, when the exposure dose was low (0-50 KGy), the curing degree Tg increased slowly. When the exposure dose increased above 50 KGy, both curing degree and Tg of the prepreg material increased remarkably until the exposure dose reached about 90 KGy. However, after this stage, both curing degree and Tg stayed plateau at about 70 % and 45 °C, separately.

The reason for this phenomenon can be explained combining the exothermic curves that shown in figure 9. The exothermic curves showed that the curing behavior of the irradiated composites changes remarkably along with the increase in EB exposure dose. There were three major exotherm peaks, α , β and γ , among which α peak only appeared in higher exposure dose samples and had a constant onset temperature of about 45°C, whereas β and γ peaks, with a onset temperature of about 150°C, only appeared in samples that cured mostly by thermal heating within the DSC and their height and area decreased with increase in dose.

When the composites were irradiated with a certain dose, part of the initiators were decomposed and the curing reaction initially took place in a liquid medium, where bimolecular combination is the dominant mechanism of curing termination. As the Tg exceeds the curing temperature (T_c), the reaction rate was reduced by orders of magnitude as the “vitrification” effect due to the glass transition exerted a dramatic restriction on bimolecular reactions, strongly reducing propagation probability and changing the dominant termination mechanism into the monomolecular occlusion of trapped free-radicals and cations. That’s why the degree of cure and Tg stayed plateau after exposure dose of 90 KGy.

During the following heating process in DSC, when the curing temperature exceeded the initial Tg of 45°C, the trapped free-radicals and cations which were already decomposed from the initiators were released and curing reaction was reactivated, which caused the post ray-curing α peak. The post ray-curing α peak only occurs on the condition that there are trapped residual cations which are already decomposed from the initiators and the T_c exceeds the Tg. While the thermal curing β and γ peaks are

because of the two-stage thermal curing kinetics of the thermal cured samples due to the decomposition of the residual initiators by the high temperature.

This phenomenon tells us that when composites are irradiated by the low-energy EB at room temperature, the curing degree and T_g of the prepreg will not exceed a certain stage, which means fully curing of the prepreg cannot be achieved. The similar phenomenon was noticed in earlier investigations for

high-energy EB processing of composites by Raghavan et al. [16], even if the exposure dose is high to 500 KGy. During the low-energy EB radiation processing of composites, the entrapped free-radicals and cations decomposed by the EB radiation will generate potential “reaction active centers” within the prepreg, which can be easily reactivated by heating.

Fig. 9. Residual exothermic heat curves of EB irradiated composites

3.3 Effect of post-curing temperature on curing degree and T_g

One of the specific advantages of EB induced polymerization, compared to a conventional thermal process, was considered as the limited temperature rise during curing, which reduces the thermal stress during the curing. However, according to the curing characteristics of low-energy EB irradiated composites described above, due to the T_g introduced “vitrification” effect, EB irradiation of composites at room temperature cannot produce a fully cured resin with a high glass transition temperature even if the irradiation dosage is high. Especially for the low-energy EB processing, where the reaction temperature is often ambient or near-ambient, this challenge would be quite pronounced. Therefore, increase of the curing temperature or additional post-curing process is necessary to

achieve full mechanical and thermal properties for the low-energy EB cured composites.

Post curing processes with different curing temperature were carried out on the samples irradiated with different exposure dose, and the effect of post curing on the resin curing degree and T_g was investigated. Table 1 below shows the effect of post curing on the curing degree; figure 12 shows the effect of post curing on the T_g .

According to table 1, composites that irradiated with EB dose between 50-70 KGy can be fully cured with a post-curing temperature in the range of 160-200 °C. Besides, the correlation between the post-curing temperature and T_g development in the composite material in figure 12 showed that the T_g of the EB cured composites were remarkably increased by the post-curing process. The highest T_g was achieved

for the 70 KGy irradiated composite when the post-curing temperature was about 180 °C, while the Tg

of the material began to decrease above 180 °C.

Table 1. Correlation of EB dose and post-curing temperature vs. curing degree

Exposure dose(KGy)	Post-heating temperature(°C)				
	120	140	160	180	200
30	×	×	×	×	×
40	×	×	×	×	×
50	×	×	100% cured	100% cured	100% cured
60	87.7% cured	87.8% cured	100% cured	100% cured	100% cured
70	89.1% cured	93.2% cured	100% cured	100% cured	100% cured

Note: "X" means occurrence of resin bleeding during post-curing due to insufficient initial curing by EB

Fig. 10. Correlation of EB exposure dose and post-curing temperature vs. Tg

3.4 Effect of EB exposure dose and post-curing on ILSS

Preliminary investigations were carried out to find out the influence of the EB irradiation dose and post-curing temperature on the ILSS. Samples were fabricated by the proposed method with varying EB exposure and post cured with 200 °C for 1 h in an oven.

The EB irradiance dose (50-80 KGy) versus ILSS can be obtained as follows:

Fig. 11. Correlation of EB exposure dose vs. ILSS

Figure 7, 8 and table 1 tell us that the curing degree and Tg for EB irradiation dose of lower than 50 KGy is too low to introduce enough tacking between layer during layup, so initial EB exposure dose of higher than 50 KGy was applied during the tape placement process for the ILSS investigations.

The results showed that the higher the incident irradiance dose, the lower the ILSS property of the composites. Further SEM investigations on the fracture surface micrographs of the ILSS samples in figure 12 shows that there are some areas within the sample where the fibers are not fully wetted by the resin. This is considered mainly due to several factors, including the impregnation quality of the

initial prepreg material, the initial radiation curing

state by the EB, compaction and post-curing process.

Fig. 12. Fracture surface micrographs from interlaminar short beam shear samples

The first factor due to the phenomenon is considered to be the fast curing speed by EB radiation. During the conventional thermal curing in autoclave, the prepregs are cured under high pressure by a programmed heating profile, which enables resin mobility to fully impregnate the fibers before cure. While in the in-situ EB curing process, the initial curing by EB irradiation is finished relatively fast, so there is not enough time for the resin to flow between the fibers and fully impregnate them. Therefore, it requires a higher quality state for the impregnation and wetting of the fibers by the resin within the prepreg material. The second factor is the lack of infiltration mechanism of the resin between the adjacent layers due to the layer-wise curing process. Especially, with the increase of EB irradiation dose, the infiltration of matrix resin driven by compaction between curing and cured layers grew worse above a certain curing degree, which results in poor wetting between fiber and matrix and poor adherence between adjacent layers.

Other samples were fabricated by the proposed method with EB exposure dose of 50 KGy and post cured with different post-curing temperatures for 1 h in an oven. The post-curing temperature vs. ILSS can be obtained as follows:

Fig. 13. Correlation of post-curing temperature vs. ILSS

The composites that post-cured with temperature of 180 °C for 1h showed the highest ILSS properties of about 63 MPa. The effect of post-curing temperature can be explained combining the correlation of EB exposure dose and post-curing temperature vs. Tg in figure 10: the Tg reached to the maximum value when the post-curing temperature is 180 °C, which means the fully curing of the composites. While Tg began to decrease above 180 °C, which is assumed to be caused by the resin matrix degradation by the high temperature. Therefore, the degradation and micro cracks introduced within the matrix and between the matrix-fiber interface by the high temperature would definitely decrease the mechanical properties of the composites.

4 Conclusions

This paper explored a new low-energy EB cured tape placement process for OOA fabrication of thermoset polymer matrix composites. This process integrates automated tape placement method with a self-shielded low-energy (150 KeV) EB irradiation unit for the on-line curing of the prepregs.

(1) A low-energy EB cured tape placement system was set up and irradiation process was optimized to obtain a homogenous curing of the prepreg. The results show that when the irradiation energy is 125 KeV, homogenous dose-depth distribution can be obtained for the prepreg material with a thickness of 0.125 mm.

(2) The curing characteristics of prepreg by low-energy EB irradiation were characterized, and the effect of EB irradiation dose and post-curing temperature on the curing degree and T_g was obtained. The results show that the low-energy EB cured composite material cannot reach to fully cured state at room temperature: curing degree and T_g stayed at about 70 % and 45 °C, even if the EB irradiation dose was high. After post-curing with a temperature of 180 °C, fully cured composites with a T_g of above 175 °C could be obtained.

(3) The effect of EB irradiation dose and post-curing on ILSS was investigated. Finally, composite plates with maximum ILSS of 63 MPa were obtained for samples that irradiated with EB dose of 50 KGy and pos-cured with a temperature of 180 °C for 1 hour.

According to the preliminary result, the method proposed in this paper has been proved as an efficient and low-cost way to fabricate thermoset composites, and has great industrial potential in OOA curing of high-performance advanced polymer composite. In the future, further investigations will be carried out the effect of the EB irradiation dose on the consolidation speed and curing degree. At the same time, the combination between the EB initiated curing and post-curing processes will be optimized to fully integrate with the tape placement process to improve the interlaminar bonding of the adjacent layers and increase the mechanical properties of the fabricated composites. Moreover, compaction, which is one of the critical factors for the impregnation and interlaminar bonding of the

composites during the tape placement, will be investigated and combined with the curing process.

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